

Research Article

Bioacoustica: Composing Animal Sounds Using Artificial Intelligence to Foster Environmental Education

Muzamil Mustaffa^{1*}, Sarina Hashim², Nurul Syahirra Roslan³, and Nur Sabrina Norizam⁴

¹ Faculty of Applied Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) Cawangan Pahang, 26400 Bandar Jengka, Pahang, Malaysia; mmuzamil@uitm.edu.my; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0557-2097>)

² Faculty of Applied Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) Cawangan Pahang, 26400 Bandar Jengka, Pahang, Malaysia; hsarina@uitm.edu.my

³ Faculty of Applied Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) Cawangan Pahang, 26400 Bandar Jengka, Pahang, Malaysia; 2022663888@student.uitm.edu.my

⁴ Faculty of Applied Sciences, Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) Cawangan Pahang, 26400 Bandar Jengka, Pahang, Malaysia; 2023104309@student.uitm.edu.my

* Correspondence: mmuzamil@uitm.edu.my; +6094602000 extension 2643.

Abstract: *Animal sounds or bioacoustic study focuses on monitoring and identifying the animal, but advances in artificial intelligence (AI) have created new opportunities for bioacoustic composition. This project aims to record animal sounds and apply AI to compose music known as Bioacoustica in a variety of musical genres. Artificial intelligence methods, SUNO AI were used to convert natural sounds into organized musical compositions, Bioacoustica. Total of 12 animal sounds were successfully recorded for two weeks sampling in UiTM Cawangan Pahang, Kampus Jengka and 12 AI Bioacoustica music also have been successfully composed. The findings demonstrate that AI capable incorporate animal sounds into music, Bioacoustica while retaining important sound qualities. Finally, Bioacoustica offers great and fascinating potential for digital sound synthesis, environmental appreciation, conservation and education.*

Keywords: Bioacoustica; animal sounds; artificial intelligence (AI).

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1. INTRODUCTION

Bioacoustics is an interdisciplinary field that studies sound in animals (Erbe, 2016). Bioacoustics research focuses on the creation, transmission and reception of acoustic signals (Brown & Riede, 2017). In recent years, technological advancements have led to the establishment of artificial intelligence (AI) approaches in bioacoustic monitoring and analysis. Thus, this enables researchers to effectively process huge amounts of acoustic data (Stowell *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, AI-generated music can replicate natural soundscapes and even combine aspects of pop, classic, jazz, beat, rhythm and blues (R&B) and hip hop. Although AI is increasingly used in bioacoustic monitoring, the limited studies have investigated its role in composing bioacoustic sounds within various musical genres. Most studies focus on environmental acoustic analysis (Kahl *et al.*, 2021) and classification of animal calls based on AI (Stowell

et al., 2019). Therefore, the objectives of this project are to record animal sounds or bioacoustic and compose an AI-generated music, Bioacoustica.

2. MATERIAL & METHOD

Project has several materials and methods for sampling and analysis;

2.1 Recording animal sounds

Animal sounds or bioacoustic data were collected through direct field recordings using smartphones during daytime and at night for 2 weeks in selected area in UiTM Cawangan Pahang, Kampus Jengka. Documentation of the places were included for each recording session. The places namely are Kolej Tok Gajah (KTG), Infra Science Tech (IST), Fast Track (FT), library, Taman Herba and Pejabat Pembangunan Infrastruktur & Infostruktur (PPII). The recorded audio files were then transferred to a computer, cleaned, formatted into wav format and the best sound output were selected for further analysis.

2.2 Bioacoustica - Composing AI-generated music

The best sound output was used to produce an AI generated music. The audio editor software, Audacity, was used for audio processing. The cleaned audio is then composed by using SUNO AI, an outstanding tool for music and audio generation. From this software, AI models with different genres such as rock and ballad (R&B), pop, beat, hip-hop, jazz and pop were composed.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Bioacoustic records

From the sampling, total of 12 sounds have been recorded (Table 1). The number sound recordings are 2, 6, 2 and 2 respectively for insects, birds, frogs and others (unidentified animals). The greatest number of sounds recorded were at Kolej Tok Gajah (KTG).

Table 1. Number of animal sounds recorded in UiTM Cawangan Pahang, Kampus Jengka.

	Kolej Tok Gajah (KTG)	IST	Fast Track (FT)	Library	Taman Herba	PPII
Insects	1	1	0	0	0	0
Birds	2	1	1	1	1	0
Frog	1	0	0	0	0	1
Others (unidentified animals)	1	0	1	0	0	0

3.2 Bioacoustica – music from animal sounds composed by AI

A total of 12 Bioacoustica, music was successfully composed by SUNO AI (Table 2) and among the music outputs are in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Two Bioacoustica (music) composed by SUNO AI.

Table 2. Bioacoustica (music) composed by SUNO AI based on location and type of animals.

Location	Sound Composed	QR Code
1. Kolej Tok Gajah (KTG)	Genre : Sound of birds (R&B) https://qr.me-qr.com/U7F6tM0O	
2. Taman Herba	Genre : Sound of birds (Jazz) https://qr.me-qr.com/toY6m5f0	

3. Infra Science Tech (IST)	Genre : Sound of insect (Jazz) https://qr.me-qr.com/91Im2vjj	
4. Infra Science Tech (IST)	Genre : Sound of birds (Pop) https://qr.me-qr.com/bSor1hM2	
5. Pejabat Pembangunan Infrastrukturu & Infostruktur (PPII)	Genre : Sound of frogs (Beat) https://qr.me-qr.com/bxeGg190	
6. Fast Track (FT)	Genre : Sound of frogs and insects (Hip-hop) https://qr.me-qr.com/advzOMjr	
7. Kolej Tok Gajah (KTG)	Genre : Sound of monkeys and birds (Pop) https://qr.me-qr.com/56VUIVp6	
8. Kolej Tok Gajah (KTG)	Genre : Sound of birds (Jazz) https://qr.me-qr.com/A4R2j2da	
9. Kolej Tok Gajah (KTG)	Genre : Sound of frogs (Hip-hop) https://qr.me-qr.com/P2B359q4	

10. Kolej Tok Gajah (KTG)	Genre : Sound of insects (Beat) https://qr.me-qr.com/ZhWHM1IB	
11. Library	Genre : Sound of birds (Classic) https://qr.me-qr.com/qDnn2Kru	
12. Fast Track (FT)	Genre : Sound of birds (R&B) https://qr.me-qr.com/KOCMpJbL	

4. DISCUSSION

Bioacoustica, the music composed by SUNO AI, are an interesting fusion of technology, art, and environmental concern. Table 1 shows the number of sounds recorded in selected area in UiTM Cawangan Pahang. Different areas contain various kinds of animal's sounds that have been recorded. Kolej Tok Gajah contains the most recordings in every category, making it the most acoustically diverse site in the collection. Additionally, it illustrates the possibility of AI composing bioacoustic sounds using natural sounds with animal sounds incorporated to diverse music genres. The structure, rhythm and pattern of the synthesized bioacoustic music are influenced by various musical styles. AI technology employed to reformat the natural sound sources of bird and insect and amphibian to several musical genres that produced or re-created new music formats by preserving their original features. Artificial intelligence has also been shown to manipulate and enhance acoustic data streams from bioacoustic applications for differing purposes (McLoughlin *et al.*, 2019). The organization and reception of bioacoustic sounds were shaped by a range of musical genres. In this work the approach is limited for classical and jazz birdsongs. It will still generally emphasize melody and smooth chord changes. On the other hand, the insect and frog calls were manipulated by the rhythmic science of hip hop and beat remixers.

There are several possible uses for combining AI-generated bioacoustic compositions with various musical genres. These works can be used as interactive resources in conservation and education to raise understanding of biodiversity. As reported by Farina & Gage (2017), bioacoustic data are used to assess biodiversity and environmental changes. This has consequences for musical compositions that focus on conservation. However, the absence of a standardized method in ecoacoustics often restricts the consistency and transferability of study findings between investigations (Vella *et al.*, 2022). The use of bioacoustics in music may contribute to conservation aims by raising awareness about environmental challenges. Some composers and sound artists use actual environmental or animal recordings to demonstrate the effects of climate change and habitat loss.

Additionally, it has potential in virtual environments, creative media and sound therapy where soundscapes are inspired by nature. To create immersive soundscapes, musicians mix genuine animal sounds into their works (Rothenberg, 2019). AI models are also important to evaluate bioacoustic patterns to develop new forms of music, thus improving computational creativity (Mirinda & Matthias, 2020). Therapeutic and mindfulness-based music use natural sounds such as rainforest ecosystems and ocean waves. This is crucial to ensuring that individuals enjoy the sound of nature as a kind of meditation.

From the environmental education point of view, this type of sound composition becomes an important tool to give prominence to the biodiversity and fragility of the ecosystems. Many studies have also highlighted how soundscapes promote encounters between people and nature (Krause, 2012; Pijanowski *et al.*, 2011). Mimicking the sounds of other animals including bird song and insect chirping, AI makes it possible to fashion bioacoustic narratives that appeal to people emotionally, particularly in urban and disconnected settings. AI applied also to sound ecology that fits well with current research movements in ecoacoustics and digital conservation. These fields examine how sound can track, visualize, and enhance empathy for ecosystems (Farina, 2018). AI-produced soundscapes could be disseminated internationally, without the constraints of field recording, to increase outreach and inclusivity in environmental storytelling.

It have pedagogical implication for these compositions. It can be utilised as an educational tool in schools, encouraging curiosity on animal activity, habitation conservation and environmental degradation. Recent studies have shown that the exposure to nature sounds in addition to visual images could be associated with psychological health and pro-environmental behaviour (Benfield *et al.*, 2014; Zhang *et al.*, 2023). The artificial nature and realism of AI-generated animal sounds such as this Bioacoustica, offers an unprecedented chance to simulate biodiversity, attracting contextually diverse participants, and prompting contemplation over the loss of species.

5. CONCLUSION

Bioacoustica effectively demonstrates how artificial intelligence (AI) can be applied to produce bioacoustic music by integrating natural animal sounds into diverse musical genre. This project effectively gathered actual bioacoustic recordings and employed AI methods to produce music, Bioacoustica. These bioacoustics animate animal sounds, enabling us to gain deeper insights and appreciation for the richness of our surroundings. They can serve as effective instruments in education and conservation, providing greater access to nature, particularly for individuals who may not encounter it directly. Although there are still uncertainties regarding the accuracy of AI in depicting real ecosystems, this method demonstrates significant promise in fostering curiosity, empathy, and an enhanced dedication to safeguarding biodiversity. Future studies should focus on expanding Bioacoustica's relevance to conservation and education, both locally and internationally.

Acknowledgments: The authors express gratitude and thanks to the Deputy Rector, Academic Affair Department, staff and students of Centre for Sciences Studies, Faculty of Applied Sciences, UiTM Cawangan Pahang for this successful study.

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